

Prevention of Drug Adolescents with Group Assertiveness Training

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Abstract: The development of drug trafficking and abuse lately, has reached an alarming situation, because victims of drug abuse are not only adults, students but also high school students, junior high school students up to elementary level students. Data in Banyumas Regency in 2018 there were 92 people carried out Rehabilitation due to drug abuse. It is of concern that 64% of them are young people aged 15-20 years and the average status as a student. Drug abuse among adolescents is caused by three factors namely environmental factors, individual teenage factors and substance factors. Early intervention in children can reduce the risk of drug abuse. One of the interventions to prevent the increase of drug users in adolescents is to improve adolescent communication skills with parents, peers and the environment with assertive therapy. The purpose of community service is to apply the results of Group Assertiveness Training research to improve interpersonal skills and self-esteem of adolescents, the ability of early drug use for drug prevention. The benefits of community service include improving adolescent mental health and reducing the risk of drug use in adolescents. The target of community service in this activity is all class students and BK teachers, Sekolah Menengah Pertama N 2 Banyumas Regency. The activities were carried out in 5 stages, namely preliminary activities, NAPZA socialization, assertive therapy, students' creativity in making posters about NAPZA as well as post tests and follow up plans. The results of devotion show the average score of student assertiveness before Group Assertiveness Training 106.72 and after 112.57. There was an increase in score of 5.8. The advice given is that Group Assertiveness Training can be used as one of the therapies to reduce the risk of drug use in school children.

Keywords: *Prevention of Drug, Group Assertiveness Training.*

1. Introduction

Teenagers are the nation's generation who will continue the development and ideals of the nation, whether or not a country is advanced or not, one of which is the participation of teenagers in realizing the nation's hopes (Reis et al.,2021; Shubnikova et al.,2017). However, teenagers nowadays are quite apprehensive in their daily social life, let alone getting to know drugs, of course this will all have a tremendous impact if it is not nurtured from an early age, this is our collective obligation to supervise and protect today's youth (Edalati & Conrod, 2019; Andrade et al.,2019).

The problem of drugs in Indonesia is still something that is urgent and complex. In the last decade this problem has become widespread. It is proven by the significant increase in the number of drug abusers or addicts, along with the increasing disclosure of drug crime cases, which are increasingly diverse in pattern and the more massive the syndicate network is (Perlmutter et al.,2018; Ischenko & Alekseeva, 2017). The impact of drug abuse not only threatens the survival and future of the abuser, but also the future of the nation and state, regardless of social, economic, age or educational strata. Until now, the level of drug trafficking has penetrated at various levels, not only in urban areas but has touched rural communities (Kumpfer & Magalhaes, 2018).

The use of narcotics and illegal drugs (drugs) among adolescents is considered to be concerning. Not only that, the number of drug users in the capital city of DKI Jakarta is also quite high. Based on data from the National Narcotics Agency (National Narcotics Agency) 2.2% of the total population of people in Indonesia are entangled in drugs. This

is based on the results of the latest research by the National Narcotics Agency and the University of Indonesia (UI). In Central Java Province, there are about 500 thousand people who are involved in the abuse of these illegal drugs. Meanwhile, drug use in the DKI Jakarta area reaches 7% and is the highest number compared to other cities. Other cities average only 2.2% of users of the total population, a difference of 4.8% compared to Jakarta.

Until now, the spread of drugs is almost unavoidable. Considering that almost the entire world's population can easily get drugs from irresponsible people. For example, from drug dealers who like to find prey in school areas, discotheques, brothels, and gang gathering places. Of course this can make parents, mass organizations, the government worry about the spread of drugs that is so rampant (Ballester et al.,2020).

Drug abuse is considered to be quite alarming in the current era of globalization, especially for the younger generation to the detriment of the nation's development, especially at the city, provincial, regional levels and even into villages. Drug abuse is a human behavior problem, not just a substance or drug problem itself. As a behavioral problem, there are many variables that influence it (Snijder et al.,2018). Therefore, information about the dangers of drugs to children and adolescents must be disseminated since a person grows up, even if a teenager is left unattended and receives less attention from parents and teachers and the community, it is feared that there will be a paradoxical effect (on the contrary), namely an increase in deeper curiosity. and have a tendency to try it on teenagers (Newton et al.,2017).

But despite all of the above, teenagers use drugs because drugs make them feel good, comfortable and comfortable at the beginning of use. The feelings produced by drugs are what users are looking for at first. Teens don't see the bad effects of drug users. now do not believe the bad consequences or harm, as adults say. The bad effects were only felt after several uses, but at that time there had been addiction and drug dependence that was ready to destroy the nation's generation (Undiyaundeye & Basake, 2020; Noar et al.,2020).

Deputy for prevention of the National Narcotics Agency (National Narcotics Agency) Ali Djohardi said 80 percent of Indonesian people know the types and dangers of drugs. But strangely, the level of drug abuse in Indonesia is still high.): Ecstasy, XTC, Inex. Group II psychotropics such as amphetamine, methamphetamine (shabu) tablets and crystals (ice). Group III psychotropics such as cecobabital, amobarbital. Class IV psychotropics such as LEXO (Bromazepam), MG (Nitrazepam) and DUM (Nitrazepam).

The development of drug trafficking and abuse recently has reached an alarming situation, because the victims of drug abuse are not only adults, students but also high school students, junior high schools to elementary school students. From research and from daily experience in dealing with drug addicts, in general, a person starts using drugs when he is a teenager, aged 13-14 years. Data from the National Narcotics Agency in 2008 cited by BKKBN (2102) shows that there were 115,404 drug users up to 2008, 51,986 of whom were adolescents aged 16-24 years. According to Agus Untoro as the Head of the National Narcotics Agency, K said that in Banyumas Regency in 2018 there were 92 people undergoing rehabilitation for drug abuse. What is worrying is that 64% of them are young people aged 15-20 years and on average are students (Muzaki, K, 2018). This condition is very dangerous considering the negative effects caused by drugs.

The National Narcotics Agency (2005) revealed that drug abuse is related to three factors. These factors are: (1) environmental factors that include disharmony with parents, drug-prone environment, lack of social control, and peer group pressure; (2) individual factors that include the desire to try, want to be accepted, follow trends, seek temporary pleasure, seek attention, and follow idol figures; (3) substance factors that include physical and psychological dependence, are easy to obtain, and relatively inexpensive. Individual and environmental factors predispose to drug behavior in adolescents. Early intervention in this child can reduce risk and change the developmental path. If you are a teenager where attitudes and behavior are already established, it is much more difficult to intervene (Sanchez et al.,2017; Ssewanyana et al.,2020).

One of the interventions to prevent the increase in drug users in adolescents is to improve the communication skills of adolescents with parents, peers and the environment. The action taken is assertive therapy. This therapy increases self-esteem, adolescent knowledge and assertiveness skills (Freddo et al.,2018; Nash et al., 2020). In addition, the development of adolescents' personal and interpersonal competencies can be done by Assertive Training. Interpersonal aspects or the ability to perform social relationships with other people identified as playing an important role in abuse the drug in adolescents is low assertiveness in adolescents, low assertiveness is not able to deal with group pressure.

State Junior High School 2 Sokaraja is one of the State Junior High Schools in the Sokaraja District, Banyumas Regency. The number of male students is 469 and female students are 450. From the results of a preliminary study, several juvenile delinquencies that have occurred are smoking, truancy. The area of Junior High School 2 Sokaraja is close to the main provincial road and the sub-district center. This makes it easier for students to interact with various human backgrounds.

Based on the description above, the servant is interested in conducting research with the title "Drug Prevention in Adolescents with Group Assertiveness Training".

2. Method

This research is quantitative. The design used in this study was "Quasy experimental pre posttest with control group". The study was conducted to determine the effect of Group Assertiveness Training on assertiveness ability to prevent alcohol abuse in adolescents. The target population in this study were all teenagers of Junior High School 2 Sokaraja. The population of each school is an average of 300 students. The sampling technique is total sampling, all students who have a history of consultation in counseling guidance or the presence of risk factors, either because of family conditions, economics and others are included as respondents. The number of samples was 100 people who were divided into 2 groups (50 intervention groups and 50 control groups).

The research instrument was in the form of an assertive ability questionnaire sheet The Hundred Assertiveness Schedule (RAS). Assertiveness scores range from 30 to 180. To prove the research hypothesis, look at the difference in assertiveness ability scores for the prevention of adolescent alcohol abuse before and after treatment in the intervention group and the control group using a paired t test. While the difference in assertiveness

ability scores before and after the intervention group and the control group used an independent t test (Gaete et al., 2021).

3. Result and Discussion

The characteristics of community service participants are in the age range of 13-15 years. The other results explain the assertiveness score in 8th grade students of Junior High School 2 Sokaraja. Community service activities regarding drug prevention in adolescents through Group Assertiveness Training get the results according to table 1.

Table 1. Assertiveness Ability Scores Before, After Group Assertiveness Training N X Junior High Schools Sudents in 2019
(n=100)

Variable	n	Mean	Primary School	Min-Max
Before	100	106.72	9.48	78-129
After		112.57	9.95	86-135

Source: Data Proceed

From table 1. it is found that the average student assertiveness score before Group Assertiveness Training is 106.72 and after 112.57. There is an increase in the score of 5.85. The lowest assertiveness score before Group Assertiveness Training was 78, the highest. while after Group Assertiveness Training the lowest score was 86 and the highest was 135.

This section discusses the assertiveness scores of the two groups before and after the intervention. The range of scores that may be obtained by respondents is 30-180. This community service got the results of Group Assertiveness Training 106.72 and after 112.57. There is an increase in the score of 5.85.

There are several reasons why teenagers use drugs, these can be grouped as follows: 1) Anticipatory beliefs, namely the assumption that if they use drugs, people will judge themselves to be great, mature, follow fashion, and so on; 2) Relieving beliefs, namely the belief that drugs can be used to overcome tension, anxiety, and depression due to psychosocial stressors; and 3) Facilitative or permissive beliefs, namely the belief that drug use is a lifestyle or habit due to the influence of the times or changes in values (Chuang et al.,2017; Kebbe et al., 2020). So that's acceptable.

For this reason, the reason for drug use begins with false perceptions, assumptions or beliefs that continue to develop in the community. Teenagers do not want to understand and do not accept facts or facts that can be proven scientifically and legally. However, regardless of all these reasons, teenagers who abuse drugs, because teenagers are offered by someone or a group of peers, to want to try or use it. Offers occur in casual situations in everyday life: on the street, in a food stall, in a bar, at a discotheque, in a mall, at a friend's house and so on. Therefore, teenagers and young children need to be aware of various situations. offerings and knowing the difference between facts and myths that develop about the dangers of drugs and the consequences for their users.

So that this emotional and sensational thing is also an easy target for producers, dealers, dealers, backers, and promoters, to trade drugs illegally, because the profits are very large and tempting for drug business people. Seeing drug organizations running very well. Once a black market is formed, it is difficult to break the chain. Drug trafficking is part of an international crime network. The cause of someone falling into drug abuse according to Libertus Jehani and Antoro (2006) is caused by many factors, both internal and external.

Internal factors, namely factors that come from a person's self consisting of: 1) Personality. If a person's personality is unstable, not good, and easily influenced by others, it is easier to fall into drug abuse; 2) Family, if the relationship with the family is not harmonious (broken home) then a person will easily feel hopeless and frustrated; and 3) Economic, difficulty in finding a job creates a desire to work as a drug dealer. Someone who is economically capable enough, but lacks sufficient attention from family or enters in the wrong environment is more likely to fall into a drug user.

Furthermore, External Factors, namely the causative factors that come from outside a person who influence in carrying out an action, in this case drug abuse. The external factors themselves include: 1) Association, peers have a strong enough influence on drug abuse, usually starting with friends joining in, especially for teenagers who have a fairly weak mentality and personality; and 2) Social/ Community, a well-controlled community environment and having a good organization will prevent drug abuse, and vice versa if the social environment tends to be apathetic and does not care about the surrounding environment, it can lead to rampant drug abuse among teenagers.

Juvenile delinquency is usually carried out by teenagers who fail to undergo the processes of mental development, both during adolescence and in childhood. Childhood and adolescence are very short, with rapid physical, psychological and emotional development. Psychologically, juvenile delinquency is a form of unresolved conflicts in childhood and adolescence. Often it is found that there is trauma in the past, harsh and unpleasant treatment from the environment, as well as trauma to environmental conditions, such as economic conditions that make him feel inferior.

Therefore, young people in society should be careful with disguised promotional events by people who do not have good intentions. Counseling that shows addicts being drunk, or experiencing withdrawal symptoms and looking miserable, even dying in a hospital with a tense atmosphere, a picture that is not in accordance with the everyday facts in the community so that teenagers become careless.

Risk behavior in adolescents such as drinking alcoholic beverages is influenced by many factors including individual personality such as lack of self-confidence and low self-esteem. Adolescents with low self-esteem usually consider themselves worthless so that they will do negative things or act according to groups that they think are ideal even though the public view is otherwise to cover up their insecurity. The results of this study indicate that there is a relationship between conformity self-esteem and alcohol drinking behavior in adolescents (Cipto & Kuncoro, 2013). Another factor, namely the lack of social skills such as dealing with fear, low self-esteem, and feeling depressed can trigger the emergence of high-risk behavior in adolescents (IDAI Youth Task Force, 2013).

Feinberg, Jones, Cleveland and Greenberg (2012) grouped the risk and protective factors for substance abuse such as alcohol into seven indices, namely community

protection, school protection, peer risk, family risk, family harmony, individual antisocial behavior and individual antisocial attitudes. The results of research conducted by Onya, Tessera, Myers and Flisher (2012) show that feeling valued by the wider community is a factor that can protect adolescents against the initiation of alcohol use. In contrast, anti-social behavior in adolescents, crime and violence in the community are significant risk factors for the initiation of alcohol use.

One of the factors of alcohol abuse in adolescents can be prevented through assertive training. Mehanovic et al., (2021) says that assertiveness training can be useful for increasing self-assessment and others, increasing self-esteem (being able to be yourself and accepting oneself), reducing anxiety, increasing the ability to make life decisions, expressing things verbally and nonverbally. Adolescents are able to make decisions to reject negative things for themselves, including alcohol. Based on the results of the study that assertiveness has an important role in the handling of users of drugs and alcohol. According to Townsend (1993) the development of assertiveness can be done through positive self-knowledge, relaxation, visualization and appropriate communication skills (Shek et al., 2020). Another way to increase assertiveness is with CBT and psychological skills training.

Assertive training given to the intervention group was carried out in groups, covering 4 sessions, where each session went through the stages of describing (explaining behavior), modeling (examplng), role playing (practicing), feedback (feedback), transferring (practicing in real life). The group discussion method is also considered suitable for teenagers compared to just counseling. Adolescents are a critical group which requires information according to the needs and motivations of the audience. For groups of teenagers, through discussion techniques reciprocal interactions can occur, growing a more interactive group atmosphere (Fakhrudin et al., 2020).

The model of learning through experience carried out in assertive training allows adolescents to learn more easily. According to Kolb (1989, in Afiatin, 2004) states that the experiential learning model allows individuals to learn as a whole, which involves the functions of cognition, affection and conation. The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Duncan et al. (2009), which concluded that assertive training can improve interpersonal communication skills of elementary and junior high school students. According to Oh's, et al (2017) the ability of Unibraw psychology students increased significantly after assertive training (pre-test score 103.68 and post-test 122.45).

While Valente's research (2017) showed the results of the AJI program (Assertive, Jaya and Innovative training) in increasing self-esteem, activity and knowledge of adolescents about drugs for drug abuse prevention in adolescents. The AJI program uses the experiential learning model more effectively than drug counseling (lectures and questions and answers). Assertive training in this study also uses hands-on practical learning experiences in addition to listening.

In this study, both groups were given counseling about the dangers of alcohol and how to prevent it, while in the intervention group, assertive training was added. Knowledge gained through counseling and assertive training is important. Knowledge or cognitive is a very important domain in shaping one's actions (overt behavior). From research it is evident that behavior based on knowledge will be more lasting than behavior that is not based on knowledge (Notoatmodjo, 2007). In addition to providing

knowledge, behavior change strategies are carried out through participatory discussions as is done in assertive training. According to Notoatmodjo (2007) behavior change strategies can be carried out by using force, providing information and discussing participation, both reproduction and association.

4. Conclusion

The characteristics of community service participants are in the age range of 13-15 years. The average score of student assertiveness before Group Assertiveness Training was 106.72 and after 112.57. There is an increase in the score of 5.85. All participants participated in the Group Assertiveness Training until it was finished. Group Assertiveness Training can be used as a therapy to reduce the risk of drug use in school children. Need props about the dangers of drugs in schools that are easily accessible to students, to remind students about the dangers of drugs to the future.

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